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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

Bo'lajak chet tili o'qituvchilarining innovatsion pedagogik kompetentligini rivojlantirish mexanizmi	10
<i>Mirzaraxonova Maftuna Ibroximjon qizi</i>	
Elementlarini integratsiya qilish: nazariy va amaliy yondashuv	13
<i>Ne'matov Karimjon Shavkat o'g'li</i>	
O'qish savodxonligi darslarida kitobxonlik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning innovatsion yondashuvlari ...	19
<i>Mahmudova Shoira Shavkat qizi</i>	
O'zbek milliy musiqasi asosida talablarda estetik did va ijro madaniyatini rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	25
<i>Gadoyeva Muborak Jumaqulovna</i>	
O'quvchilarning yozuv kompetensiyasini baholash mezonlarini takomillashtirish masalalari.....	30
<i>Abdurashidova Xafiza Abdurashidovna</i>	
Xurshid Do'st Muhammad qissalarida rivoyatchi strategiyasi.....	34
<i>Uzoqova Nargiza Yuldosh qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tanqidiy fikrlashni shakllantirishda innovatsion texnologiyalarining ahamiyati	37
<i>Eshpulatov Shakir Nabiyevich, Ahrorova Ozoda Amriddinovna</i>	
"Xonada o'simliklarni o'stirish" intellekt xaritasi (Mind Map) yordamida o'quvchilarda ekologik tarbiya va ijodiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish	41
<i>G'aniyev Abduqahhor Gadoyevich</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishda amaliy mashg'ulotlarning tashkiliy-pedagogik jihatlari.....	46
<i>Joldasov Ixtiyor Suyundikovich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda iqtisodiy tarbiyani shakllantirishning zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalari	50
<i>N. Asadov</i>	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarni tayyorlashda kreativ kompetentlik va kasbiy muvaffaqiyat o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik mezonlari.....	53
<i>G. Xamidova</i>	
Gamifikatsiya elementlarining bakalavr talabalarini raqamli resurs yaratishga motivatsiyasiga ta'siri	56
<i>Maxkamova Dilshodaxon Xabibjon qizi</i>	
The Influence of Family Parenting Style on the Formation of Primary School Students' Personality	59
<i>Berdiyeva Mohloroyim Mirzohid qizi</i>	
Noto'liq oilalardagi onalarning tarbiyaviy uslublari va farzandlarining ijtimoiy-psixologik moslashuvi (O'zbekiston namunasida).....	64
<i>Ismoiljonov Ravshan Baxtiyor o'g'li</i>	
Raqamli pedagogika sharoitida interfaol ta'lim metodlari asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetentligini shakllantirish.....	69
<i>Jumaniyozova Donoxon Olimboyevna, Bekmuratova Muhayyo Uralbayevna</i>	
Matematika ta'limida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning metodik asoslari.....	73
<i>Mirzayeva Shahlo, Qodirova Muattar Ithom qizi, Rovshanova Yulduz Shovkat qizi</i>	
O'qishga motivatsiya tushunchasi uning nazariy-psixologik tahlili.....	77
<i>Azimova Rushana Zokirjon qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'lim talabalarida akademik prokrastinatsiyaning prediktorlari: akademik motivatsiya, umid va shaxs xususiyatlari	81
<i>Shodiboyev Shohruh Shuhrat o'g'li</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida rivojlantiruvchi markazlar integratsiyasini ta'minlash metodikasi.....	86
<i>Qahhorova Sevara Alimardonovna</i>	
O'quvchi-yoshlarni virtual olam ta'siridan himoya qilishning nazariy asoslari.....	90
<i>Isayeva Gulii Parpiyevna, Ravshanov Umidjon Abdiqodir o'g'li</i>	

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida matematik tafakkurni oshirishda mantiqiy masalalarning o'rni	93
<i>Xilvatova Go'zal Sultonovna</i>	
Pedagogika tarixini o'qitishda talabalarda tarixiy tafakkurni rivojlantirish	97
<i>Jurayev Bobomurod Tojiyevich</i>	
Bolalarda ona tilida tinglash hissini rivojlantirish usullari	101
<i>Nurmatova Muxlisa Akmal qizi</i>	
Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida ingliz tilini o'qitish samaradorligini oshirish (Kahoot, Quizlet va Moodle platformalari misolida)	106
<i>Yusupova Shahnoza Abduxafizovna</i>	
Sport maktablarida 16–18 yoshli nayza uloqtiruvchi sportchi-qizlarda portlovchi kuchni rivojlantirish	111
<i>Tursunova Surayyo Botir qizi</i>	
Umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasalarida pedagog kadrlarning uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanishini ta'minlashda "Kasbiy rivojlanish kuni" va "Kasbiy rivojlanish soati" tadbirlari: amaliyot tahlili	115
<i>Gaffarov Azizjon Muhammadsaidovich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti direktorlarining faoliyatini samarali tashkil etishning nazariy jihatlarini (Learning outcomes) asosida	124
<i>Rabbimova Shaxnoza Soyib qizi</i>	
Bo'lg'usi o'qituvchilarda axloqiy madaniyat fazilatlarini qaror toptirishning pedagogik mexanizmlari	128
<i>G'aniyeva Sayyora Saidmurod qizi</i>	
Yengil atletikachilarning musobaqa jarayonida tibbiy-pedagogik monitoringini takomillashtirish	132
<i>Mamadaliyev Abror Akbarjonovich</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt yordamida rus tilini o'qitish va uning samaradorligi	137
<i>Yagafarova Nazilya Rafailovna, Nazarov Sardor, Onorboyev Kamronbek</i>	
O'quvchilarda ilmiy dalillarni tahlil qilish va xulosa chiqarish kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish metodikasi	142
<i>Baymurotova Mukaddas Xamdorovna</i>	
Ilmiy muxokamalarda pragmatik kompetentlikning roli	150
<i>Eshbo'riyeva Aziza Muhiddinovna</i>	
Talabalarda kognitiv-pragmatik kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish metodikasini takomillashtirishning mazmuni	155
<i>To'rabekova Aziza Mirzabek qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda motivatsiyani shakllantirishda interaktiv metodlarning o'rni	159
<i>Qamchibekova Roziyaxon Xasanboy qizi</i>	
Проблема разграничения понятий "концепт" и "понятие" в современной лингвистике: лингвосомиотический и когнитивно-дискурсивный анализ	164
<i>Якунина Ангелина Алишеровна</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari asosida amaliy bezak san'ati naqsh elementlarini raqamli qayta ishlash va arxivlashtirish	169
<i>Jabbarov Rustam Ravshanovich</i>	
Bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarining yozuv kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda Design Thinking texnologiyasining metodik imkoniyatlari	176
<i>Amanbayeva Oydin Urazali qizi</i>	
Tez qalamchizgi mashqlarida psixologik-pedagogik yondashuvlarning ahamiyati	181
<i>Suyunov Navro'z Alisher o'g'li</i>	
Innovatsion yondashuv orqali bo'lajak tasviriy san'at o'qituvchilarining metodik tayyorgarligini rivojlantirish konsepsiyasi	186
<i>Xalilov Lenar Shevketovich</i>	
Tarbiya fani asosida o'quvchilarda huquqiy kompetentlikni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari	190
<i>Jumanova Xafiza Xoliqulovna</i>	
Samarqand arxitektura-qurilish instituti va shahar infratuzilmasi rivojlanishi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik (1950–1990-yillar)	195
<i>Abulqosimova Dildora Asrorovna, O'ralov Sodiqjon</i>	
Rivojlanishida nuqsoni bor bolalar ta'limida ikkilamchi cheklovlarni kamaytiruvchi ta'lim texnologiyalari	199
<i>Qo'ziyeva Shahnoza Muhammadsoli qizi</i>	

O'quvchilarda milliy g'oya va mafkurani rivojlantirishda mumtoz musiqaning o'rni va ahamiyati	202
<i>Baymanova Feruza Abralovna</i>	
Ommaviy jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishning pedagogik asoslari	207
<i>Xayitova Ulfatoy Tursunovna</i>	
Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarida ijtimoiy faollikni shakllantirishning pedagogik mexanizmlari	211
<i>Turg'unboev Sirojiddin Faxriddinovich</i>	
Muhandislik ta'limida Bernulli va Puasson taqsimotlarini texnologik jarayonlar misolida o'qitish metodikasi ...	216
<i>Qo'ziboyeva Nozima Yoqubjon qizi, Maxmanazarov Sardor Toirjon o'g'li, Saydullayev Asadbek Xayrullo o'g'li</i>	
Психолого-педагогические основы обучения теме “производная” в курсе алгебры и начал анализа президентской школы	225
<i>Шахноза Холмуродова Зоир кизи</i>	
O'qish savodxonligi darslarida Bloom taksonomiyasi va 4K kompetensiyalarining integrativ modeli	234
<i>Farsaxonova Mastura Jalol qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida ta'lim sifatini baholash mezonlari va monitoring tizimini takomillashtirish: indikatorlar asosidagi boshqaruv modeli	241
<i>Jo'rayeva Dilrabo Kamoliddin qizi</i>	
Maxsus mashqlar yordamida start tezligini oshirish metodikasi	244
<i>Sitora Elova Axmatqulovna, Panjiyeva Gulzoda Eshdaviat qizi</i>	
Amudaryo foreli (<i>Salmo trutta oxianus</i>) O'zbekiston hududida tarqalishi va ekologiya ta'siri	248
<i>Xaqberdiyeva Shoira Tursunaliyevna, Xolmo'minova Sevinch Sirojiddinova, Qurbonazarova Marjona Zokirovna</i>	
Suv va quruqlik muhitiga moslashgan amfibiyalarda adaptatsiya xususiyati	251
<i>Xaqberdiyeva Shoira Tursunaliyevna, Axmamatova Feruza Shamsiddin qizi, Qo'ldoshova Ruxshona Navro'z qizi</i>	
O'zbekistonda tarqalgan kaptarsimonlar xilma-xilligi, ularni tarqalishi, biologik xususiyatlari va amaliy ahamiyati	255
<i>Xaqberdiyeva Shoira Tursunaliyevna, Xolmo'minova Jasmina Baxtiyor qizi, Saidova Dilnoza Rustamovna</i>	
Surxondaryo viloyatidagi qo'lqanotlilar turlarining morfologik tasnifi va hududiy farqlari	259
<i>Xaqberdiyeva Shoira Tursunaliyevna, Yarashova Sarvara Islomovna, Bahromova Shahzoda Abduqodirovna</i>	
Игровые технологии как средство активизации коммуникативной деятельности учащихся на занятиях по русскому языку	267
<i>Халикова Гульбахор Исановна</i>	
Yoshlarni pedagogik kasbga yo'naltirish ishlarini o'rganishning konseptual va metodologik asoslari	270
<i>Matkarimova Muxabbat Abuovna</i>	
O'qish savodxonligini baholovchi topshiriqlar turlari	277
<i>Rasulova Mushtariybonu</i>	
Qoraqalpog'istonning shimoliy tumanlaridagi bolalarda tashqi nafas olish tizimi xususiyatlari	281
<i>Orazbaeva Navbaxor Mratbaevna</i>	
“Kompyuter tarmoqlari” fanini o'qitishda dasturiy-didaktik vositalardan foydalanish	285
<i>Muqimov Shahzodbek Ixtiyor o'g'li</i>	
Yangi O'zbekiston: yangilanish va taraqqiyot omillari (Qashqadaryo viloyati misolida)	288
<i>Shomirzayev Maxmatmurod Xuramovich, Safarova Sevara Saloxiddinovna</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim strategiyalaridan foydalanib o'qish samaradorligini oshirish	294
<i>Narzullayeva Gulzira Xayrullo qizi, Abdusottarova Farog'at Olimjon qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'limda “Zoologiya” kursini innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalar asosida o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirish (“umurtqali hayvonlar” misolida)	299
<i>Xonnazarova Mamlakat To'lqinovna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ommaviy sportni rivojlantirish strategiyalari	303
<i>Xudoyberganov Javlonbek Soatboy o'g'li</i>	
Accommodating a Teenage English Learner With Tourette-Related Stammering in Uzbekistan State Multilevel Test Preparation: A Single-Case Study	307
<i>Yulduz Sultanova</i>	
Yengil atletikada to'siqlar osha yugurish texnikasini takomillashtirish va o'rgatish uslubiyati	313
<i>Chariyev Ulug'bek Abdujabbarovich, Radjabov Jaxongir Furkatovich</i>	

The Interaction of Language and Culture in Intercultural Conflict Communication	317
Gulnoza Khushnazarova	
O'smir shaxsida o'zini o'zi tushunish psixologik muammo sifatida.....	321
Mahmudov Abdurasul	
O'quvchilar nutqida milliy-madaniy leksik birliklarni qo'llashga o'rgatishda semantikashtirish	325
Tursunova Javhar Bakir qizi	
Kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida boshlang'ich ta'limda matematik madaniyatni shakllantirish: Qori Niyoziy merosi asosida.....	329
Axmedova Nargiza Toychibekovna	
A2 darajadagi o'quvchilarda kommunikativ ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishda adaptiv yondashuvning roli	333
Nezametov Zuxra Axmadovna	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda pedagogik kasbga ijodiy munosabatni tarbiyalashning nazariy asoslari.....	336
Axmatov Ibrohimjon Furqat o'g'li	
Voyaga yetmaganlar profilaktikasida maktab, oila va mahalla hamkorligining zamonaviy holati va diagnostikasi	340
Japparbergenova Indira Bayramovna	
Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarining ijtimoiy va intellektual kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishni pedagogik tizimini takomillashtirish	344
Amankosova Dinara Gabitovna	
Innovatsion usullar vositasida maktabgacha yoshdagi duduqlanuvchi bolalar nutqini rivojlantirish.....	348
Mamatova Aziza Bo'riboevna	
Dzyudoning olimpiya o'yinlaridagi o'rni va ahamiyati	353
Jaxongir O'razbayev Temur o'g'li	
Umumta'lim maktab o'quvchilarida milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarga integratsiyalashgan harbiy tarbiyaning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	356
A'zamov Inom Salimjonovich	
The Role of Digital Platforms in Developing Students' Independent Learning Competency.....	360
Jo'rayeva Zamira Ishmuminovna, Uraqova Shaxlo Turdiyevna	
Shaxsiy ta'lim trayektoriyasi tushunchasining pedagogik-psixologik mohiyati	365
Toshpo'latov Olim Panjiyevich	
"Ilk qadam" davlat o'quv dasturi asosida maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida faoliyat markazlarining ta'lim jarayonlarini tashkil etish	370
Bektemirova Asilabonu Akmal qizi	
Kreativ ta'lim texnologiyalari asosida talabalarda innovatsion kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish metodikasini takomillashtirish	374
Sariboyev Nurali Abdunazarovich	
Bolalarning tanqidiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishga ta'sir etuvchi omillar va yosh xususiyatlari	378
Erkinboyev Muhammadqodir Nodirbek o'g'li	
Tasviriy san'at darslarida eshitishda nuqsoni bo'lgan o'quvchilarning badiiy-ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish.....	383
Xushvaqtov Abror Doniyor o'g'li	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida zamonaviy o'qitish metodlari va interaktiv texnologiyalardan foydalanishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	387
Murodova Dilafro'z Matmurod qizi, Sattarova Bibijon Muzaffar qizi, Bekmurodova Muhayyo Uralbayevna	
Kredit-modul tizimida o'quv-me'yoriy hujjatlarni takomillashtirish borasidagi milliy va xorijiy tajribalar	391
Aralova Maxsuma Abdurahmonovna	
Yuqori sinf o'quvchilariga chet til o'qitish va o'rgatishda motivatsiyaning o'rni xususida.....	396
Atadjanova Shaxnoz Abbasovna, Ismoilova Feruza Salimjon qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqini rivojlantirishda innovatsion metodlar	400
Axmedova Fayziniso Otabek qizi	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarning uzluksiz amaliy faoliyatida professional salohiyatini rivojlantirish yo'llari	403
Habibullayeva Muxlisaxon Yorqinjon qizi	

Innovatsion yondashuv asosida bo'lajak texnologiya o'qituvchilarining PR kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	406
J. B. Jumabayev	
Raqamli pedagogika sharoitida interfaol ta'lim metodlari asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetentligini shakllantirish.....	412
Jumaniyozova Donoxon Olimboyevna, Bekmuratova Muhayyo Uralbayevna	
Biologiya ta'lim jarayonida ilg'or hamda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni samarali qo'llash.....	416
Mo'minov Dilshod Yaxshiboy o'g'li	
Oliy ta'limda masofaviy ta'limning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari	420
Mutalibova Muqaddasxon Abdunabi qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda raqamli platformalar orqali kiberxavfsizlik madaniyatini shakllantirish	423
Nazarmatova Dilshoda Umarali qizi, Saminjonova Sevaraxon Axmadjon qizi, Abdihakimova Muqaddas Fahridinova, Matsapayeva Nigora Satbay qizi	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining etnopedagogik kompetentligini shakllantirishda milliy hunarmandchilik va xalq amaliy san'atining didaktik imkoniyatlari	428
Pardayeva Gulchexra Safarovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning bilish kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari	432
Qipchaqova Sevinchxon Farxodjon qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim boshqaruvida ERP tizimlarini integratsiyalashning proaktiv modeli.....	436
Raxmatillayev Oyatillo Zikrillayevich	
Maktabgacha ta'limda rivojlantiruvchi markazlarni tashkil etish va loyihalashtirish	439
Sadikova Shoista Akbarovna, Yangiboyeva Salomat Samandarovna, Yangiboyeva Sevinch Samandarovna	
Milliy hunarmandchilik buyumlarini yasash orqali o'quvchilarning ijodkorligini rivojlantirish	442
Xayitov Jonibek Xolboboyevich, Nabijonova Nilufar Nabijon qizi	
Futbol o'yinida to'pga kalla bilan zarba berish.....	446
Xolmaxmatov Boburjon Musurmon o'g'li	
Сравнительно-типологический анализ юмора и гуманизма в творчестве Гафура Гуляма и Марка Твена.....	451
Абдумунинова Махлиё	
Особенности фонетико-фонематической речи (качественные и количественные) у младших школьников с речевыми расстройствами.....	453
Заирова Н. Б.	

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL PLATFORMS IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT LEARNING COMPETENCY

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Abstract: This study explores the role of digital platforms in developing students' independent learning competency in higher education institutions of Uzbekistan, including Navoi State University. A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining surveys and interviews conducted among undergraduate students. The findings indicate that digital platforms positively contribute to students' self-management, motivation, goal-setting, and learner autonomy. In addition, the study emphasizes the significance of interactive feedback and collaborative digital tools in enhancing independent learning processes.

Key words: digital platforms, independent learning, learner autonomy, higher education, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur tadqiqot O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim muassasalarida, jumladan Navoi State University talabalari orasida mustaqil ta'lim kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda raqamli platformalarning o'rnini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Tadqiqotda aralash metodologiya qo'llanilib, bakalavriat talabalari o'rtasida so'rovnoma va intervyular o'tkazildi. Natijalar raqamli platformalar talabalarning o'zini boshqarish, motivatsiya, maqsad qo'yish hamda mustaqil o'rganish ko'nikmalariga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishini aniqladi. Shuningdek, mustaqil ta'lim jarayonlarini qo'llab-quvvatlashda interaktiv fikr-mulohaza va hamkorlikka asoslangan raqamli vositalarning ahamiyati ta'kidlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli platformalar, mustaqil ta'lim, o'quvchi avtonomiyasi, oliy ta'lim, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация: Данное исследование посвящено изучению роли цифровых платформ в развитии компетенции самостоятельного обучения студентов высших учебных заведений Узбекистана, включая Navoi State University. В исследовании применялся смешанный метод, включающий анкетирование и интервьюирование студентов бакалавриата. Полученные результаты показали, что цифровые платформы оказывают положительное влияние на самоорганизацию, мотивацию, целеполагание и автономность обучающихся. Кроме того, была подчеркнута значимость интерактивной обратной связи и цифровых инструментов совместного обучения в поддержке процессов самостоятельного обучения.

Ключевые слова: цифровые платформы, самостоятельное обучение, автономия обучающихся, высшее образование, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

Independent learning is considered one of the most important competencies in modern education. Today's students are expected not only to receive knowledge from teachers but also to manage their own learning processes, solve problems independently, and adapt to rapidly changing educational and professional environments (Holec, 1981; Zimmerman, 2000). In the digital era, the ability to study independently has become especially important because students have access to large amounts of information and online educational resources.

The development of digital technologies has significantly transformed higher education systems around the world. Various digital platforms, including Learning Management Systems (LMS), Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), educational applications, and online collaboration tools, provide students with new opportunities to learn beyond traditional classroom settings. Platforms such as Moodle, Google Classroom, Canvas, and Coursera allow students to access learning materials anytime and anywhere, communicate with peers and instructors, and organize their learning activities more flexibly (Means et al., 2013).

Digital platforms are particularly important for developing independent learning competency because they encourage students to plan their studies, monitor their progress, search for educational resources, and evaluate their own performance. Features such as online quizzes, automated feedback, discussion forums, and

progress-tracking systems help learners become more active and responsible participants in the educational process.

In Uzbekistan, improving the quality of higher education and integrating digital technologies into the learning process have become major priorities of educational reforms. The “Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System until 2030” emphasizes the importance of preparing independent, competitive, and lifelong learners capable of adapting to modern global challenges (Ministry of Higher Education, 2022). As a result, universities across the country have increasingly introduced digital learning environments and blended-learning approaches.

Despite the growing use of digital platforms in Uzbek higher education institutions, there is still limited empirical research examining how these technologies influence students' independent learning competency. Most existing studies focus mainly on the technical advantages of digital education rather than its impact on learner autonomy and self-regulated learning skills. Therefore, further research is needed to understand which digital tools and pedagogical practices most effectively support independent learning among university students in Uzbekistan.

This study aims to investigate the role of digital platforms in developing students' independent learning competency. The research focuses on four major dimensions of independent learning: goal-setting and planning, self-monitoring and reflection, resource management, and intrinsic motivation.

Research Questions

1. To what extent do digital platforms contribute to the development of independent learning competency among Uzbek university students?
2. Which digital platform features most effectively support learner autonomy?
3. What pedagogical conditions are necessary for digital platforms to enhance independent learning?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Independent learning has become an important concept in modern educational research. Holec (1981) defined learner autonomy as the ability of students to take responsibility for their own learning processes. This idea emphasizes that learners should actively participate in setting goals, selecting learning strategies, monitoring progress, and evaluating outcomes rather than depending completely on teachers.

One of the most influential theoretical frameworks related to independent learning is Zimmerman's (2000) Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) theory. According to this theory, effective learning occurs through three interconnected stages: planning and goal-setting, monitoring learning activities during performance, and reflecting on learning outcomes. Students with strong self-regulated learning skills are generally more motivated, organized, and academically successful (Pintrich, 2000). They are also better prepared for lifelong learning and adaptation to changing professional environments.

Researchers have emphasized that independent learning competency includes several important dimensions, such as time management, self-monitoring, motivation, critical thinking, and resource management. In higher education, these competencies are especially important because university students are expected to complete many academic tasks independently and continuously develop their knowledge outside the classroom environment.

The rapid development of digital technologies has transformed traditional teaching and learning processes. Digital platforms such as Moodle, Google Classroom, Canvas, Coursera, Zoom, and Microsoft Teams provide flexible opportunities for communication, collaboration, and independent study.

Bower (2008) explained that digital platforms contain specific “affordances,” meaning features that can either support or limit educational activities. Many scholars argue that these technological features can positively influence independent learning behaviors when used effectively.

For example, adaptive feedback systems help students identify mistakes and improve their understanding independently (Azevedo & Hadwin, 2005). Open-access educational resources and online repositories provide students with opportunities to search for information and learn beyond classroom materials (Conole & Alevizou, 2010). Collaborative tools such as discussion forums, shared documents, and group projects encourage communication, peer learning, and reflective thinking, which are important components of self-regulated learning (Vygotsky, 1978).

In addition, learning analytics and progress-tracking systems allow students to monitor their academic development and manage their learning goals more effectively (Siemens & Long, 2011). Therefore, digital platforms are increasingly viewed not only as technological tools but also as important environments for developing learner autonomy and independent learning competency.

In Central Asian countries, the integration of digital technologies into higher education has grown significantly in recent years. However, the effectiveness of digital learning environments differs depending on institutional resources, internet accessibility, and students' digital literacy levels.

Dzhaksybekov and Seitkali (2020) investigated digital transformation in Kazakhstani universities and found that unequal digital infrastructure and limited technological skills affected the success of online education. Similarly, Mamatov et al. (2021) reported that Uzbek students participating in blended-learning environments demonstrated higher levels of learner autonomy compared to students studying in traditional classrooms.

Although these studies provide important insights into digital education in the region, they do not clearly explain which specific digital platform features contribute most strongly to the development of independent learning competency. In addition, empirical research focusing specifically on Uzbek university students remains limited.

Therefore, the present study seeks to fill this research gap by examining how different digital platform features support independent learning competency among students in Uzbekistan's higher education system. The study also explores the pedagogical conditions necessary for digital platforms to effectively promote learner autonomy and self-regulated learning.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-methods research design in order to investigate the role of digital platforms in developing students' independent learning competency at Navoi State University. The research combined quantitative and qualitative approaches to obtain both statistical data and detailed explanations of students' experiences with digital learning technologies.

The quantitative stage of the research was conducted first through an online survey. After analyzing the survey results, qualitative interviews were organized to provide deeper insights into the findings and better understand students' perceptions of digital platforms and independent learning.

The participants of the study consisted of 214 undergraduate students studying at Navoi State University. The sample included students from different academic years and fields of study, including pedagogy, information technology, economics, and natural sciences. Among the participants, 118 were female and 96 were male. The average age of the respondents was approximately 20 years. For the qualitative phase of the research, 24 students were selected to participate in semi-structured interviews in order to gather diverse opinions and experiences.

Several research instruments were used during the study. The first instrument was the Independent Learning Competency Scale (ILCS), which was adapted from the Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire developed by Pintrich et al. (1991). The questionnaire included 32 statements measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." The scale focused on four major dimensions of independent learning competency: goal-setting and planning, self-monitoring and reflection, resource management, and intrinsic motivation.

The second instrument was the Digital Platform Engagement Index (DPEI), designed to measure students' use of digital learning technologies. The questionnaire examined the frequency and effectiveness of different digital tools, including Learning Management Systems (LMS), MOOCs, collaborative platforms, educational videos, and digital assessment systems.

In addition, semi-structured interviews were conducted to explore students' personal experiences with digital platforms. The interview questions focused on learning motivation, self-management, interaction with digital tools, and difficulties encountered during online and blended-learning processes.

Data collection was conducted during the second semester of the 2024–2025 academic year. The questionnaires were distributed online through Google Forms over a three-week period. Participation in the research was voluntary, and all participants were informed about the purpose of the study before completing the survey.

After the quantitative stage, interviews were conducted through Zoom and lasted between 35 and 55 minutes. With participants' permission, all interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed, and translated into English for analysis.

The collected quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS Version 27. Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression analysis were applied to examine the relationship between digital platform engagement and independent learning competency. The qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis in order to identify the main themes and patterns emerging from students' responses.

To ensure reliability and validity, the coding and interpretation processes were carefully reviewed, and ethical principles related to confidentiality and voluntary participation were fully observed throughout the research process.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The quantitative results showed that most students actively used digital platforms in their learning processes. Learning Management Systems (LMS), such as Moodle and Google Classroom, were used more frequently than other digital tools, while participation in MOOCs was comparatively lower. Overall, students demonstrated a moderate level of independent learning competency. Among the different aspects of independent learning, intrinsic motivation was the strongest area. Many students reported that digital platforms increased their interest in learning and encouraged them to study more independently. However, self-monitoring and reflection skills were comparatively weaker, indicating that some students still experienced difficulties in evaluating and organizing their own learning progress.

The analysis also revealed a strong positive relationship between digital platform engagement and independent learning competency. Students who used digital platforms more actively generally demonstrated stronger skills in planning their learning, managing educational resources, and completing tasks independently.

Regression analysis further confirmed that digital platforms significantly influenced the development of independent learning competency. In particular, LMS platforms and collaborative tools, such as shared documents, discussion forums, and group communication applications, had the strongest positive impact on students' autonomous learning behaviors. Educational videos and MOOCs also contributed positively, although their influence was less significant. Digital assessment tools showed the weakest effect compared to other platform features.

Many participants explained that LMS platforms helped them organize their studies more effectively. Course schedules, assignment deadlines, and progress indicators enabled students to plan their weekly learning activities and better understand course requirements. One participant stated:

"Before using the LMS, I only focused on what the teacher explained in class. Now I can see all tasks and deadlines clearly, so I can plan my learning independently."

Students emphasized that immediate feedback on assignments and quizzes helped them recognize mistakes and improve their performance. Automated quiz results and teacher comments encouraged self-reflection and independent correction of errors. At the same time, several students reported dissatisfaction with delayed or overly general feedback, explaining that ineffective feedback reduced their motivation and made self-improvement more difficult.

Collaborative digital tools, including discussion boards and shared documents, increased students' motivation and responsibility. Participants noted that working together online encouraged active participation and helped them learn from peers' ideas and experiences. Students also mentioned that visible group participation created a sense of accountability, motivating them to contribute more consistently to academic tasks.

Despite the advantages of digital platforms, students identified several challenges. The most common problems included unstable internet access, particularly in regional areas, limited digital skills, and insufficient training on how to use educational platforms effectively. Some participants also noted that certain instructors used platforms only for uploading lecture materials instead of creating interactive learning environments. According to students, this limited the potential of digital platforms to support independent and active learning.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, this study demonstrated that digital platforms play an important role in developing independent learning competency among students at Navoi State University. The findings revealed that students who actively use digital learning platforms tend to show stronger abilities in goal-setting, self-management, resource organization, and learning motivation. Digital tools such as Learning Management Systems, collaborative platforms, and educational resources create more flexible and student-centered learning environments that encourage learner autonomy.

The study also showed that the effectiveness of digital platforms depends not only on the technology itself but also on several educational and institutional factors. Instructor support, interactive teaching methods, students' digital literacy, and stable internet access are essential conditions for promoting successful independent learning. When digital platforms are used only for sharing lecture materials, their educational potential becomes limited. Therefore, universities should focus on integrating more interactive and learner-centered digital practices into the educational process.

The results of this research are particularly important within the context of ongoing higher-education reforms in Uzbekistan and the goals of the national Higher Education Development Concept until 2030. The integration of digital technologies into higher education can support the preparation of independent, responsible, and lifelong learners capable of adapting to the demands of modern knowledge-based society.

Despite its contributions, the study has several limitations. The research was conducted only at Navoi State University and involved a limited number of participants. In addition, the study mainly relied on self-reported data, which may influence the objectivity of the findings. Future research should include larger and more diverse samples from different universities and apply longitudinal or experimental research designs to examine the long-term impact of digital platforms on independent learning competency.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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